
Techniques of Optical Character Recognition

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ABSTRACT

Optical character recognition involves recognition of a character from printed or written text. The need for converting printed and hand written documents have increased due to high cost of storage, complexity of accessing and classifying data and spoilage of paper documents. By digitalising the documents in electronic format eliminates the problem of space and time. There are many techniques by which OCR can be implemented efficiently. This paper discusses some of the prevalent techniques and their limitations. Some of the techniques include Support Vector Machines, Artificial Neural Networks and Deep convoluted neural networks. Support vector machines used statistical learning algorithms to identify text characters. Backpropagation nets with hidden units are used for classification part of the character recognition using ANNs. They are efficient in skewed and noisy texts.

Keywords

Optical character recognition, pattern recognition, image processing

INTRODUCTION

The Optical Character recognition(OCR) technique is a technique by which a machine recognises, differentiates and classifies printed or written text characters. It is an essential requirement for digitalising documents which are actually in paper format. The crux of OCR involves image processing and pattern recognition. The need for converting printed and hand written documents have increased due to high cost of storage, complexity of accessing and classifying data and spoilage of paper documents. By digitalising the documents in electronic format eliminates the problem of space and time. Contents of various ancient historical scriptures are preserved by using Optical character recognition techniques. Many corporate organisations and institutions incorporate this technique into their software programs to hustle their data entry processes. It works significantly in reducing the human error. However, the program has to have high accuracy, time efficiency and needs to be monitored consistently to prevent unrecognised data entry. There are many techniques by which OCR can be implemented efficiently. This paper discusses some of the prevalent techniques and their methods of implementation.

Document Inputs

The paper documents are at first converted to electronic format through images or by photo-scan. Digital cameras and optical scanners are used for creating inputs and their conversion.

Image Pre-processing

Every input image has a certain level of noise associated with it. Image pre-processing in OCR includes image cleaning routines to remove noise and garbage, optimisation of images from digital cameras, dual page splitting, different algorithms for skew correction up to 20 degrees, built-in adaptive binarisation and texture filtering.^[2] Next, the images are required to be converted into grayscale, which are then binarised in accordance to the threshold value. Binarisation is the conversion to binary format, a binary image which consists of 1's and 0's. 1's denotes the black pixel of the image and 0's denotes the white pixel of the image. Thresholding in OCR allows image segmentation into two pixels: foreground and background pixels. Foreground pixels correspond to the text and the background pixels correspond to the remaining segments of the image.^[1]

Fig 1: Steps of Optical Character Recognition

Segmentation and Feature extraction

The cardinal part of the processing stage is segmentation. Segmentation allows the character recogniser to extract the features from the image represented for each and every single character. Segmentation identifies the important features through threshold value. Morphological operators remove the flecks and holes and provides only the pixels with maximum and relatively high threshold pixels. They correctly shape and cut the exact pixels out to get high accuracy and reduce confusion. The work of feature extraction is to reduce the redundant pixels and white pixels. By this way the size of the document can be increased vastly.

Post Processing

Characters recognised are usually separate in nature. As single entities, they don't provide much information. After the processing stage, the characters which belong to the same string are grouped together to form words and sentences, which provide concrete meaning. The grouping is based on the location of the character in the input document. Characters that are located close enough sufficiently are grouped together. [3]

OPTICAL CHARACTER RECOGNITION USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS

The goal of artificial neural networks in OCR is to assort the characters of the given image into alphanumerical and special characters mainly in English or any other trained languages, and ultimately to machine editable format. Artificial neural networks helps in classifying stroke edge, long breaks and backgrounds where the unnecessary gaps or space can be avoided. The strokes are retrieved from the image-character by character and are matched or compared to obtain positively accurate results. There are possibilities for errors due to handwriting because sometimes the characters are connected and concatenated, (cursive handwriting) where identifying and classifying every single character becomes difficult. Even in cases where the ink is blotted during writing or printing processes, the recognition of characters becomes difficult.

Fig 1: Training and Testing processes using ANNs

Training process

The technique artificial neural networks used in OCR, involves two major functions such as training and testing. Training is simple if a dataset is provided. Training involves pre-processing, feature extraction and model estimation. Pre-processing requires the original electronic handwritten document to be converted to grayscale (If inputs are already in grayscale, continue as such). Then the grayscale document undergoes binarisation where it is converted to binary format, which consists of 1's and 0's. 1's denotes the black pixel of the image and 0's denotes the white pixel of the image. The cardinal part of the pre-processing stage is segmentation. Segmentation allows the character recogniser to extract the features from the image represented for each and every single character. Segmentation identifies the important feature through threshold value. Morphological operators remove the flecks and holes and provides only the pixels with maximum and relatively high threshold pixels. They correctly shape and cut the exact pixels out to get high accuracy and reduce confusion.

Testing processes

Testing includes pre-processing, feature extraction and classification. The work of feature extraction is to reduce the redundant pixels and white pixels. By this way the size of the document can be increased vastly. Even the spaces between the words are adjusted respectively. For model estimation from a finite set of feature vector, a model is created for each class of training data. This is currently implemented using MATLAB where it can be implemented using two methods. The first method is manual instruction method, where the instruction for all these steps are given manually and visualising the results through work screen. The second method is done using graphical user interface where the process is automated and simultaneously visualised. The final image can be even viewed in RGB, main window, crop to edge etc.

Classification Techniques

Classification forms the cardinal part of this technique. The classification was based on different properties of the characters. These variations were derived from the text input. Texts with little or no difference in character heights were classified based on varying widths. ^[6]

M.Usman Raza et al. ^[4] proposed that the classification was carried out based on the width of the letters. Different characters had varying lengths. The characters were classified roughly based on the approximate width ranges. They used the Nearest neighbour algorithm to classify based on variable width and fixed height range. They used a back propagation neural net with three layers- input, hidden and output with dynamically varying number of neurons for each training epoch. The number of neurons in the hidden layer were optimised using various methodologies. Their work concluded that more classification patterns produced more accurate results.

Fig 3: Classification using character width

M.M. Farhad et al. ^[5] used the differing properties of curvature of the symbols. The shape of the character or symbol and the distance of the symbol from the corners of image are different for different symbols. The number of featured points required to distinguish a symbol from the like symbols and to accurately recognise it are given by the varying angles of seeking. The angular deviation between the featured points is determined. This method was found to particularly efficient with highly skewed and noisy input images.

Fig 4: Extraction using seeking angle of Symbol ‘A’

OPTICAL CHARACTER RECOGNITION USING SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINES

Support Vector Machines(SVM) is a machine learning technique in artificial intelligence which implies supervised learning models affiliated with learning algorithms that analyse and classify data[7]. When a set of examples are given for training, the SVM classifies it into categories based on the model. This classification is successful when the learning algorithms involve statistical learning theory in it. When the data is already labelled classification becomes a easy job, but in cases of non-labeled data, supervised learning model does not help SVM. So another approach, Unsupervised learning is implemented in SVM. Unsupervised learning is a approach where the clustering of unlabelled data is done and classifying them into groups with bound to the model. This method of using clustering algorithm in SVM is called support vector clustering[8]. This method is significantly used in certain applications by industry when new data with no labels are found.

Fig 4: Steps in SVM based character Recognition

SVM is implied in Optical Character Recognition using a sequence of steps. Text embedded in the video and images sometimes may contain certain important information or dates which are needed to be extracted. These kinds of data are extracted at the first step in the image or key frame process. When large amount of data is conveyed through the image or key frame it is necessary to identify the text region

accurately in it. The difficulties faced through detection of the text region are the background, colour and size (which may vary even in a single sentence) of the text displayed.

Text Line Extraction

Text line extraction involves two sub-steps: Candidate text region extraction and Text line location. Candidate text region is an algorithm which extracts data from the image or video with respect to two characteristics of closed caption. The texture of the text is considered as a cluster of vertical and horizontal edges. The compression of these edges may sometimes result in blur parts(dilation of edges) which has varied intensity compared to background edges, but later through SVM-based text identification these blur parts can be corrected or rectified. These cluster of edges which contain data in single sentence or multiple sentence can actually be located through the second sub-step namely text line location.

Fig 3: Candidate text Regions

Text line location involves locating the text in the image or video using the top and bottom baselines of the text. These baselines are found by comparing and grouping related and similar cluster of edges. Some of the similarities considered for such comparison is height and length of edges of the text to the background edge's length and height. When there are cluster of baselines in the image, these baselines are needs to be separated and segmented into smaller regions. After segmentation each region should undergo text line extraction process. Very small regions and non-baseline regions can be neglected because they may mostly contain redundant data or background data.

SVM-Based Text identification

SVM-based text identification is the crucial part of OCR where the actual text from the image is extracted and modified using support vector machine algorithm. This part consists of two sub-steps: normalisation & feature extraction and SVM training & identification.^[9] In first step, the located candidate text lines are normalised into a certain required resolution because the origin text line may have varying resolutions. It is necessary for a SVM to normalise a text line into a single resolution for high accuracy. In feature extraction, the features of the corrected baselines are extracted using distance map of each slide or region, which acts as the input for feature extraction. Distance map is estimated with the help of cluster of edges of text with accordance to background.

The final sub-step of SVM-based text identification is SVM training & identification which involves training the machine with myriads of text and non-text data and identifying the extracted baseline with accordance to it. A system can be trained with the input data, where the input data is converted into statistical data by the system with accordance to the nature of the input data. Identification is the process of identifying the valid baseline ranges with respect to the data provided. This process can be carried out only when a system is trained with required amount of sample training data which is a range of inputs and respective outputs. A SVM involved machine which is trained can provide the extracted text with high accuracy efficiently.

CONCLUSION

This paper reviews several methods of implementation of Optical Character Recognition. It can be said that the classification system forms the crux of the recognizing system. The reviews point to the fact that more efficient the classification system employed is, the more accurate the results are. Although these techniques are accurate to an acceptable level, a lot of productive work still needs to be carried out in favour of optimization, improved accuracy and efficiency. The techniques need to be tested with a variety of images and text with different levels of noise, skew and distortion.

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